

CHALLENGES, THREATS AND RISKS IN DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract: this article analyzes problems, threats and dangers in the conditions of digital transformation, the need and theoretical foundations of researching informational-cultural threats, socio-philosophical research of inter-ethnic harmony and solidarity in the conditions of informational-cultural struggles.

Key words: information, information-cultural threats, information-religious threats, information-psychological threats, secularism, international harmony, digital transformation, information inequality, manipulation of consciousness, information extremism, information crime.

We will list and briefly describe the new problems, threats and dangers that await people in the conditions of digital transformation and are starting to face them today. Information inequality. One of the dangers for people in the information society is the problem of information inequality. Factors of social division are accumulation, generation, use of knowledge. Not all members of the information society can make practical use of the new opportunities it can give to people. In addition, this includes not only economic and instrumental-technogenic factors, but also the ability to provide some users with access to society's informatics and information resources, but also humanitarian factors, which mainly depend on the unique qualities of a person. Such factors include: informational, including the linguistic culture of a person, informational competence, education, as well as human motivation, the desire for knowledge and self-study, and the development of intellectual abilities. After all, if a person does not want to be an active member of the information society, then no technology will help him.

The availability of information reduces the motivation to create new knowledge, develop new ways of knowing. Rejection of knowledge due to its increase in size indicates that internal personal structures are not ready for increased loads. This is manifested in the lack of skills to assess the quality, volume and depth of the received information, which leads to an increase in social inequality [1].

Mind manipulation. The second and very serious threat to man in the information society is related to the fact that the development of global

networks of television, computer communication, radio communication and other information systems creates many opportunities to influence and manipulate the public mind. By their mental nature, people are very suggestible and therefore easily subject to targeted psychological influence at the sub conscious level and therefore easily subject to targeted psychological influence at the sub conscious level. This feature is used to control a large number of people, create illusions, secretly deprive them of freedom of choice, change their minds, motivate people in the right (some group) direction [2]. Manipulation of mass consciousness is the main element of information warfare and is basically the same as introduction to individual consciousness. prepared information. Its effectiveness is reliable and clearly visible. For example, the results of election campaigns for various authorities, as well as the extensive use of very expensive advertising in television programs, are clearly visible. Research results show that television has the strongest psychological impact on a person. The reason is that the video information, in addition to influencing the human mind, directly penetrates into his subjectivity. In addition, the person himself is not worried about it and therefore cannot protect himself from this influence. This, to a large extent, is the basis of the modern methodology of mind manipulation [3].

Community virtualization. Another, still little-explored danger for humans in the context of digital transformation is the psychological phenomenon called virtualization of society. Its essence is that real physical objects, processes and events are replaced by virtual images that are very similar to echoes of objective reality, but are not. These features, as well as the high dynamism of the society's information framework, allow creating virtual reality in it. It is perceived by man, along with physical reality. A typical example here can be the so-called derivatives, that is, securities on the stock market, as well as the new virtual currency - bitcoin. Speculative exchange of shares of industrial corporations, appreciation or depreciation of exchange rates in creative financial markets - all these are widely used in the world economy today and, as the analysis shows, they threaten the sustainable development of society [4].

The virtualization of the social space and constant interference in the lives of other people with the help of social networks paradoxically leads to an increase in the feeling of loneliness "in the crowd".

Cyber diseases. In the conditions of digital transformation, another, radically new threat to man is called cyber-diseases. These include the psychological dependence of people on television, computer games, Internet addiction, etc., which have already become a drug for many in modern society.

The maniacal fascination of some young people with computer games promoting cruelty and violence is also frightening. These phenomena are the most common in information-developed countries today and are one of the negative results of the process of informatization of society. It can be considered that these events will develop as this process develops further. Already, not only addiction is developing, but symptoms of more serious diseases appear, for example, phantom ringing syndrome - it seems to a person that the phone in his bag is ringing or vibrating. Another example of a new disease. Nomophobia - "Nomobilephobia" - fear of being without a mobile phone. The disorder is on the DSM5 list of mental disorders in America. Larry Rosen explains the causes of this disease as a result of nervousness when a person is afraid of losing something.

Information crime. The formation of the information society opens many opportunities for the development of information crime, which can be directed against the individual, society and the state. This is called computer crimes, which are mainly aimed at unauthorized access to the databases of automated information systems of government bodies, financial organizations and industrial enterprises. In these systems, in the process of informing the society, a large amount of confidential information is collected not only about the activities of relevant organizations, but also about personal information about citizens of the country, their addresses, phone numbers, property, income, etc. This information is of course of great interest to criminals. and many of them already use the services of information technology professionals.

Information extremism. A sign of informational extremism is physical, material, and moral damage to the legal interests, rights and freedoms of citizens, it is emphasized in the study of R. V. Upornikov [5].

The main characteristic features of informational extremism can be mentioned: the radicality of actions; fight against society; the spirituality and immorality of the content; institutionality; distortion of political and legal thinking.

It is important that the information on the Internet is presented not only in the form of a static "picture", but also that it is characterized by activity, says researcher A.Kh. Valeev [6].

The volume and speed of information flow is attractive to organizers of information extremism. In fact, they "engage" Internet users in various discussions and debates with the specific goal of changing personal opinions, ideologies, principles, worldviews, and leading to changes in individual or group

behavior, as well as creating public opinion that is beneficial to the influential party.

"In the conditions of globalization and the informatization of society, when the obstacles in the control and management of information flows are practically removed, when the national borders of the states are raised to the level, mainly communicatively, the former extremist actions of young people are adopted to influence the minds and behavior of young people," it is said. In the researches of E. O. Kubyakin and A. N. Safronov [7].

Information terrorism. The concentration of information in automated information banks, which provides remote access to users, is one of the important directions of the process of informatization of society, as it significantly increases the efficiency of information use. However, at the same time, the possibility of unauthorized access to this data, as well as the risks associated with its theft and even intentional corruption, are also increasing. A new phenomenon in the field of information crime is information terrorism. As a result, the operation of the information system can be practically paralyzed. Most often, this situation occurs as a result of specially organized large-scale network attacks. In recent years, these attacks have been repeatedly observed using the opportunities. To solve such problems, a relatively new direction of ensuring the protection of individual information rights is developing. Such rights are already protected by the laws of a number of countries, including Russia, but the perfection and simplification of the protection procedures is still a long way off.

The battle for information. Among the threats of the information society, a very special place is occupied by information warfare, the methods and tools of which are already well developed in theoretical and practical aspects. Information wars are already a very common and effective method of conflict in politics, economy and culture. In the future, with the development of the tools and institutions of the information society, it can be assumed that information wars will become more widespread both locally and globally.

Information warfare is fighting for people's minds and hearts, with all the power of computer technology, it's just a tool. And the goal is to control people's minds in order to gain a certain power by spreading specially prepared information. Over time, an understanding of the special importance of personal communication and communication with listeners will emerge. New technologies are emerging based on the integration of different communication systems that support each other in the information conflict.

Such types of information attacks as dissemination of false information, manipulation of social consciousness, erosion of national and spiritual values, promotion of values completely foreign to mentality, destruction and change of people's historical memory, and cyber terrorism are spreading widely [8]. In this process, the world's most powerful mass media, CNN, BBC, and Reuters news agencies have a high chance. Through them, you can receive information from any part of the world and transfer it to any part. Mass media has become a powerful force today. They have the ability to lie about them and turn lies into truth. Therefore, every person must have the culture of receiving, using and transmitting information [9].

As long as humanity does not have a culture of using information, it will not be able to get out of the tracks of "terrible lies". Today, the Internet has taken over the whole world. It is important to understand its positive and negative aspects. A third of the world's population now uses the Internet. More than 12 million of them are citizens of Uzbekistan. The Internet should be viewed not as a source of truth, but as an opportunity to obtain information. Independent thinking is required to distinguish truth from falsehood in all forms of information spread over the Internet. After all, independent thinking is the main factor in the fight against ideological and informational threats, ideological immunity, high spirituality [10].

In conclusion, a number of trends that have arisen in the world require radical changes in various areas of human society, ensuring the security of information systems and the application of information technologies in the educational process. The expansion of the volume of information, the technological possibilities of its storage, processing and transmission creates the basis for their use in all sectors of society.

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